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ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION BY THE NORTHERN DATA ANALYSIS CONSORTIUM (NDAC)

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ABSTRACT

The attitude of the HIPPARCOS satellite is defined by three 'heliotropic' angles, relating the axes of the telescope to the mean ecliptic of J2000.0 and a nominal Sun direction. In the quiet intervals between jet firings, these angles are represented as continuous spline functions of time. Spline coefficients are obtained by least-squares fitting to star mapper transit times and angular rotation rates from three gyroscopes. Early in the mission, the positions of bright programme stars are progressively improved by use of the transit time residuals of the attitude solution.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the Attitude Reconstitution (AR) is to determine the full orientation of the HIPPARCOS telescope as function of time and with an *rms* accuracy of about 0.1 arcsec relative to some 'known' celestial coordinate system (in the end, the HIPPARCOS system). This accuracy is needed for the subsequent Great Circle Reductions (Paper II): the pointing of the nominal spin axis (Z) is needed to 0.1 arcsec in order to avoid significant projection errors in the primary field, while the rotation about the same axis is needed with similar precision to allow resolution of 'slit inconsistencies'. Intermediate and less accurate attitude versions are also needed for preprocessing of star mapper and IDT photon counts.

The AR is chiefly based on star mapper observations of brighter ($B \lesssim 11$) programme stars, whose positions are assumed to be known. The gyros also provide continuous information on the inertial rotation of the satellite, which may be especially valuable near the gaps in the star mapper records due to occultations by the Earth and Moon.

The accuracy of the AR cannot be much greater than that of the star positions, on which it is based. Near the beginning of the mis-

sion, it is seriously limited by errors in the Input Catalogue, and this part of the AR must be repeated later when improved positions are available. We intend to use the star mapper observations themselves for successive improvement of the working catalogue (initially equal to the Input Catalogue), so that it always contains the best positions compatible with previous observations. This will hopefully minimize the need for such repetition of the AR.

2. DEFINITIONS

The time coordinate T , used everywhere in the NDAC reductions on and above the level of individual frames, is the interval in seconds TDT from 1988 Jan 1, 12^h TDT = J1988.0 TDT. The primary celestial reference system used in the reductions is represented by the equatorial coordinate triad $N = [\mathbf{l} \ \mathbf{m} \ \mathbf{n}]$ (Murray, 1983, Ch. 4), with $\mathbf{l}$ and $\mathbf{n}$ being unit vectors toward the mean vernal equinox and mean equatorial pole of J2000.0, and $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{l}$.

The telescope triad $Z = [\mathbf{x} \ \mathbf{y} \ \mathbf{z}]$ is defined by the two projections of the grid onto the sky (Fig. 1). Let SS' be the great circle through the apices of the projections of the star mapper, and C, C' its intersections with the projections of the central slit ($G = 0$, cf. Paper II) of the primary grid. The $\mathbf{x}$ is the bisector of the acute angle CC' , $\mathbf{z}$ is normal to the great circle and pointing towards the solar-panel side of the satellite, and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{x}$.

The attitude is most generally expressed by the orthogonal 3×3 matrix $A = N'Z$. The six-fold redundancy of this matrix makes it somewhat awkward to use, and we prefer to write it as the product of elementary rotations defining three (non-redundant) Euler angles. The adopted decomposition is

$$A = A_1(\epsilon)A_3(\lambda_S)A_1(\nu - \frac{1}{2}\pi)A_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi)A_3(\Omega) \quad (1)$$

in which $A_i(\phi)$ denotes a rotation by the angle ϕ about the i th axis:

$$A_1(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c\phi & -s\phi \\ 0 & s\phi & c\phi \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_2(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta & 0 & s\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s\theta & 0 & c\theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_3(\psi) = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi & -s\psi & 0 \\ s\psi & c\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$\epsilon = 23^\circ 26' 21''.448$ is the mean obliquity of the ecliptic and λ_S the longitude of the 'nominal Sun', given by an exact formula as function of T ; these define the 'heliotropic' coordinate triad $NA_1(\epsilon)A_3(\lambda_S)$, in which the telescope triad is given by the heliotropic angles ν, ξ, Ω . This definition of attitude angles is identical to the one used by MATRA for defining the scanning law (nominal attitude), albeit the telescope triad is not defined in exactly the same way. According to the scanning law, ξ is constant (43°) while ν and Ω increase at an av-

erage rate of approximately $1.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $8.18 \cdot 10^{-4}$ rad s^{-1} , respectively, as described by simple and explicit analytical formulae.

The proper direction $\mathbf{u}$ to a celestial object (the 'apparent' direction as seen from the satellite; cf. Murray, 1983, Ch. 2.5) can be expressed with respect to $\mathbf{Z}$ by means of the field index f (± 1 for the preceding/following field) and field coordinates (w, z) , namely

$$f = \text{sign}(\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{u}), \quad w = \mathbf{y}'\mathbf{u} \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma) - \mathbf{x}'\mathbf{u} f \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma), \quad z = \mathbf{z}'\mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

with γ being an agreed-upon value for the basic angle (corrections to this value are part of the field-to-grid transformation; see Paper II).

3. TEMPORAL REPRESENTATION OF THE HELIOTROPIC ANGLES

The angles ν , ξ , Ω are continuous functions of T , which must be written in terms of a finite set of parameters for their least-squares estimation. Each angle is expressed as a superposition of simple analytical functions (polynomials and trigonometric series); thus

$$\nu(T) = \nu^{(\text{ref})}(T) + \Delta\nu(T) \quad (3a)$$

$$\xi(T) = \xi^{(\text{ref})}(T) + \Delta\xi(T) \quad (3b)$$

$$\Omega(T) = \Omega^{(\text{ref})}(T) + \Delta\Omega(T) + \delta\Omega(T) \quad (3c)$$

$\nu^{(\text{ref})}$, $\xi^{(\text{ref})}$, $\Omega^{(\text{ref})}$ are trigonometric series plus piecewise polynomials, with breakpoints at the instants of jet firings. They provide a reference attitude accurate to about 1 arcsec, which is used for the preprocessing of star mapper counts and to linearize the observation equations for the star mapper transits and gyro signals.

$\Delta\nu$, $\Delta\xi$, $\Delta\Omega$ are cubic splines, *i.e.* piecewise cubic polynomials with two continuous derivatives everywhere except at the jet thrusts. The flexibility of these splines is adjusted by inserting the proper number of knots to subdivide the jet intervals. The same knot sequence is used for all three angles and the knot intervals will probably be of the order of 100 s.

$\delta\Omega$, finally, is a correction derived in the Great Circle Reduction process (Paper II), bringing down the errors of the third angle to the milliarcsec range; it is not further discussed here.

The AR done by NDAC is numerical rather than dynamical, in the sense that Euler's dynamical equations are not explicitly used together with a torque model. However, the adopted formulation essentially allows for periodic torque components plus a linear variation over each jet interval, with approximate continuity across the thrusts. The splines furthermore allow small departures from this model.

The temporal representations described above define an independent set of Fourier, polynomial, and spline coefficients for a time interval of several hours (typically between two occultations). The AR follows by independent least-squares processing of each such interval.

4. THE REFERENCE ATTITUDE

The coefficients of the functions $\nu^{(\text{ref})}$, $\xi^{(\text{ref})}$, $\Omega^{(\text{ref})}$ are simply obtained by a linear least-squares fit to the heliotropic angles for the real-time attitude determined on board the satellite. This is available at discrete instants (sample frequency 0.9375 Hz on-board time) in the form of offset angles ϕ , θ , ψ (< 10 arcmin) with respect to the nominal attitude. The heliotropic real-time attitude angles are obtained by using the transformation

$$A^{(\text{real time})} = A^{(\text{nominal})} A_1(\phi) A_2(\theta) A_3(\psi) \quad (4)$$

in conjunction with (1).

Following the determination of the reference attitude, the star mapper photon counts are processed through the appropriate numerical filters to estimate the transit time at each slit group and the stellar flux in the two channels (B_T and V_T). The attitude is needed here to predict the transit time on which the search window will be centred, and to calculate the speed of scanning and hence the correct filters.

5. OBSERVATION EQUATIONS FOR STAR MAPPER TRANSITS

Let T_g be the transit time of a star across either group of four star mapper slits ($g = 1$ for the 'vertical' group, $g = 2$ for the 'chevron' group). The centre line of each group is described by some known equation of the field coordinates, $u(w, z) \equiv w - w_g(z) = 0$, which is by definition satisfied at the moment of transit. Using the reference attitude at the observed transit time and the proper direction as calculated from the working catalogue, we find by means of (2) a pair of field coordinates, which does not satisfy this equation, $u^{(\text{ref})} \neq 0$. The observation equation for the corrections to the reference attitude then takes the form

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu} \Delta \nu + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} \Delta \xi + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Omega} \Delta \Omega + \text{noise} = -u^{(\text{ref})} \quad (5)$$

in which the derivatives are evaluated for the reference attitude and the corrections are to be expressed in terms of the spline coefficients.

The centre line equations $w_g(z)$ are polynomials, with two segments for the chevron group, representing the 'large-scale transformation' of the star mapper grid. It is possible to include also some of

these coefficients as common unknowns over a longer time interval, thus providing a partial calibration of the star mapper geometry.

6. OBSERVATION EQUATIONS FOR GYRO SIGNALS

Three active gyroscopes measure the instantaneous inertial rotation about respective input axes, sampled twice per frame. Let Γ_r be the 3×1 matrix containing the r th gyro samples (at time T_r). With ω denoting the angular velocity of the satellite, $I = [i_1 \ i_2 \ i_3]$ the triad of gyro input axes (with $|i_1|$ the scale factor of the first gyro, etc) and β, v_r two 3×1 matrices for the gyro biases (drift rates) and high-frequency noise, we have the model

$$\Gamma_r = I' \omega(T_r) + \beta + v_r \tag{6}$$

We assume that $Z'I$ is known and constant, that β is unknown but constant over several hours, and that v_r is white noise with known s.d.

The angular velocity, expressed in heliotropic angles, is

$$\omega = k \dot{\lambda}_s + s \dot{\nu} - \langle z \times s \rangle \dot{\xi} + z \dot{\Omega} \tag{7}$$

with $\langle \rangle$ signifying a unit vector. k and s are unit vectors towards the north ecliptical pole and nominal Sun, respectively. Using the reference attitude and setting $\beta = v_r = 0$, we calculate by means of (7) and (6) a reference gyro signal and hence the observation equation

$$I's \dot{\Delta\nu} - I'\langle z \times s \rangle \dot{\Delta\xi} + I'z \dot{\Delta\Omega} + \beta + v_r = \Gamma_r - \Gamma_r^{(ref)} \tag{8}$$

in which the spline coefficients and β are the unknowns.

7. FIRST AND SECOND AR PASSES

The first pass of the AR is a linear least-squares estimation of the spline coefficients for $\Delta\nu, \Delta\xi, \Delta\Omega$ together with a relatively small number of additional parameters (gyro biases, star mapper geometry). The observation equations are (5) and (8). If the positions in the working catalogue are accurate enough, this single pass should be sufficient to reach the desired accuracy (~ 0.1 arcsec) in all axes.

With the less accurate catalogue early in the mission, the attitude errors are likely to be several times greater. Attitude and catalogue errors exceeding 0.1 arcsec have a degrading effect on the Great Circle Reductions, and it cannot be avoided that the early AR and Great Circle Reductions must be repeated with an improved catalogue. If however the errors in Ω exceed about 0.2 arcsec rms, there is also a risk that the elimination of slit inconsistencies (Paper II) will not converge. A more accurate attitude in Ω is thus required at this stage.

A second pass of the AR brings about the required improvement by including more equations like (8), but derived from the IDT data. The light modulation by the primary grid contains very accurate rate information, and can be likened to a gyro with input axis along Z and a rate bias due to any scale error of the grid. In the preprocessing of IDT counts, the first-pass attitude is used to predict the smoothed grid coordinate of each object at frame mid-time. The output of the preprocessing is an observed value of the same quantity. The time derivative of the difference *observed-predicted*, as the object moves over the field, is therefore a measure of departure from the attitude rate in the first pass and is used on the right-hand side of the observation equation similar to (8).

The least-squares solutions for both passes is made by Householder orthogonal transformations (Lawson and Hanson, 1974; Bierman, 1977). Apart from its numerical accuracy and stability, this method has significant advantages over the conventional approach using normal equations, especially when intermediate estimates (based on part of the observations) are needed and in the handling of common parameters (the *a posteriori* estimate of some parameters from a batch of observations can be handed over, in the form of triangularized data equations, as *a priori* information for a subsequent batch). Although Householder transformations become impracticable for very large problems, as in the Great Circle Reductions and Sphere Reconstitution (Paper II and III), they are well suited for the AR with its rather limited number of unknowns.

The residuals of the star mapper observation equations (5) consist to some part of positional errors from the working catalogue. If they are regarded as 'observations' of these errors, we find the following equation for the corrections to (α_i, δ_i) , the barycentric position of star i at the catalogue epoch:

$$\mathbf{d}' \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u} \rangle \Delta \alpha_i \cos \delta_i + \mathbf{d}' (\mathbf{u} \times \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u} \rangle) \Delta \delta_i + \text{noise} = [\text{res. of (5)}] \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{z} w'_g(z)$ is a vector normal to the projection of the slit group on the sky. These equations, given conservatively low weight to prevent overadjustment, are collected after the AR proper and applied to the working catalogue. This contains the previous position estimate together with its upper-triangular information matrix, number of previous updates, etc; these are all modified by the updating algorithm based on Householder transformations. Proper motions and parallaxes are not affected by this process, but the magnitudes and colours may be similarly updated from star mapper observations.

8. IMPLEMENTATION

The high-density tapes containing 'raw' data from ESOC will be sent to Royal Greenwich Observatory, where the AR along with the preprocessing

of star mapper and IDT counts is to be performed on a VAX-11/750 computer. The processing at RGO follows a weekly schedule, with approximately the following task sequence occupying five days:

- calculate reference attitude
- set up sub-catalogue (objects observed in a week)
- star mapper preprocessing
- photometric update of sub-catalogue
- AR, first pass
- IDT preprocessing
- OTF calibration and location estimator (grid coordinates)
- AR, second pass (optional)
- update positions in sub-catalogue
- merge sub-catalogue into main working catalogue

The attitude, grid coordinates and catalogue updates are forwarded by tapes to the Danish Space Research Institute, where the Great Circle Reduction and Sphere Reconstitution will be made.

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Figure 1. Projections of the primary and star mapper grids onto the sky define the telescope coordinate triad $Z = [x \ y \ z]$. x is the bisector of CC' ; z is normal to the great circle SS' .